

Quantifying Prototype Stability in ProtoPNet Without Manual Part Annotations

Iker Sancho^{1,2}[0009-0003-2184-2506], Ruben Naranjo^{1,2}[0009-0002-3924-0194],
Nerea Aranjuelo¹[0000-0002-7853-6708],
and Itsaso Rodríguez-Moreno²[0000-0001-8471-9765]

¹ Vicomtech Foundation, Basque Research and Technology Alliance (BRTA),
Mikeletegi 57, 20009, Donostia-San Sebastián, Spain

² University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), Donostia-San Sebastián, Spain
isancho@vicomtech.org

Abstract. Prototype-based networks such as ProtoPNet offer intrinsically interpretable predictions by matching regions of the inferred image to learned prototypical patches. However, existing stability metrics rely on expensive manual part annotations and are limited to narrow perturbation types. In this work, we introduce the *Structural Stability Score* (S_{ss}), a scalable, annotation-free metric that quantifies prototype stability under a diverse set of visual transformations by comparing prototype activation maps. We evaluate S_{ss} on two ProtoPNet variants (using VGG19 and Resnet34 backbones) trained on the CUB-200-2011 dataset, and assess stability across six distinct perturbations. Our results reveal clear differences in robustness both between models and among different transformations. These findings demonstrate that S_{ss} is a practical tool for highlighting stability variations within and across prototype-based networks, guiding model selection and interpretability analysis.

Keywords: Prototype-based Networks, Interpretability, Stability.

1 Introduction

In recent years, the adoption of complex machine learning models, such as deep neural networks, has yielded unprecedented performance across a wide range of tasks, from medicine [12] to autonomous driving [10]. However, the opaqueness of these “black-box” models impedes trust, accountability, and regulatory compliance, especially in high-stakes domains where understanding the rationale behind a decision is critical [18,4,9]. This growing demand for transparency [8] has motivated the development of interpretable machine learning approaches that either explain predictions post-hoc[22] or embed interpretability directly into the model architecture [1].

Prototype-based networks[6,24,11] represent a promising paradigm for intrinsic interpretability. Inspired by human reasoning, which often relies on recalling representative examples, ProtoPNet learns a dictionary of prototypical image patches and classifies new inputs by measuring the similarity between image regions and these learned prototypes [6,21]. By displaying the most relevant prototypes next to each prediction, ProtoPNet provides a clear, example-based justification: the model indicates “this part

of the image looks like that prototype”, facilitating intuitive human inspection without sacrificing performance.

However, the mere visualization of matching prototypes can hide semantic inconsistencies and fragility to slight perturbations in the input [17]. Existing measures of prototype quality, such as consistency and stability scores, are based on manual part annotations, which limits their scalability and objectivity [15,14]. To address these problems, we introduce the Structural Stability Index (S_{ss}), which leverages the Jaccard index and the distance between maximum heatpoints to compare prototype activation maps between original and perturbed images, quantifying robustness across multiple perturbation types without human labeling.

2 Related Work

Interpretable machine learning has become a critical requirement in many application domains [18], as black-box models, especially deep neural networks, can be difficult to trust or audit when making decisions [13,4]. Prototype-based networks address this need by embedding interpretability directly in the model [21]. In particular, ProtoPNet [6] learns a set of prototypical image patches and classifies new images by comparing local regions to these prototypes. This design yields a transparent reasoning process: each prediction is justified by showing the image parts that match learned prototypes, akin to how a human might recognise an object by recalling similar examples. Importantly, ProtoPNet and its variants have been shown to attain accuracy on par with conventional Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) while providing such built-in explanations [19,7,16,11,5].

Despite their promise, prototype-based explanations may require extra processes to improve their quality and robustness [2] as well as rigorous evaluations to ensure their meaningfulness and robustness. Visualising a few “matching prototypes” is not enough to guarantee interpretability in general [17].

One approach to enhance the quality of part-prototype explanation is presented in the paper “This Looks Like That, Because... Explaining Prototypes for Interpretable Image Recognition” [19]. During the inference process, rather than simply showing which patches match, this methodology provides quantitative information about the contribution that each visual characteristic (colour, shape, texture, contrast, saturation) makes to each prototype in this process. This allows for a more detailed breakdown of how each prototype encodes knowledge and how much each feature influences the model’s decision.

Other recent studies have found that learned prototypes can be fragile or inconsistent. For example, even small perturbations or distortions can cause a prototype to activate on a semantically different part of the image [15,20]. To address this issue, the paper "Evaluation and Improvement of Interpretability for Self-Explainable Part-Prototype Networks" [15] introduces two significant quantitative metrics for assessing prototype quality: the *consistency score* and the *stability score*. These metrics, respectively, measure whether each prototype corresponds to the same object part across different images, and whether that correspondence holds under slight input perturbations. However, computing these metrics requires detailed human-provided part annotations:

each prototype’s location is mapped to ground-truth object parts in every image, so the stability score (sometimes called S_{sta}) can only be evaluated with manual labelling of parts. Such manual intervention limits scalability and objectivity [3,14].

In view of these limitations, an objective methodology that ensures the correct measurement of the stability of prototypes in Part-Prototype Networks is of utmost importance, specially given the relevance of interpretable machine learning in high-risk applications.

3 Method

In this section, we first review existing metrics and enhanced explainability techniques for prototype-based models, and then, introduce our proposed metric.

3.1 Importance Scores for Image Characteristics

As explained in Section 2, in the search for improved explanations, a new approach to measure the importance of different features in the inference of an image is proposed in the paper “This Looks Like That, Because... Explaining Prototypes for Interpretable Image Recognition” [19].

Following the indications mentioned in the cited research, a closed set of transformations is defined, Φ , trying to address as many important features in an image as possible (see Eq. 1). These transformations modify contrast, saturation, hue, shapes (using a wavelet distortion effect), and texture (applying denoising techniques) as seen in Fig. 1.

$$\Phi = \{f_{\text{Contrast}}(x), f_{\text{Saturation}}(x), f_{\text{Hue}}(x), f_{\text{Shape}}(x), f_{\text{Texture}}(x)\}. \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. Transformations from the set Φ applied to a test image.

With the transformations already defined, two distinct metrics are introduced to precisely quantify the effect of specific visual features on the model’s decision process: the *local importance score*, which measures the difference in similarity score between a prototype and an original image versus the same prototype and the image modified by a specific visual transformation, and the *global importance score*, which computes a weighted arithmetic mean of these local importances across all training images, weighting each term by its prototype similarity to ensure that higher-similarity images have greater influence.

In this way, it is possible to decide which is the most influential characteristic in the classification, achieving a quantitative and precise measurement.

3.2 Stability Score

Prototype evaluation via qualitative human studies (where multiple annotators score visual characteristics under strict guidelines) is rare and resource-intensive. To address this, Huang et al. (2023)[15] propose two different scores to evaluate the **interpretability** of Part-Prototype Networks: **(1) Consistency**, which tests whether a prototype activates on the same object part across different images. **(2) Stability**, which tests whether a prototype activates on the same part of an object before and after perturbing an image. In this work, we focus exclusively on the the Stability metric (S_{sta}) defined in Eq. 2.

$$S_{sta} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{j=1}^M \frac{\sum_{x \in \mathcal{I}_{c(j)}} \mathbb{1}\{\mathbf{o}^{p_j}(x) = \mathbf{o}^{p_j}(x + \xi)\}}{|\mathcal{I}_{c(j)}|}. \quad (2)$$

For each prototype p_j , it is observed how many parts of the object remain within the activation performed on the original image, $\mathbf{o}^{p_j}(x)$. Then, the process is repeated on the disturbed image, $\mathbf{o}^{p_j}(x + \xi)$ (where ξ is Gaussian noise) and each part of the object is compared (Fig. 2 is a visual representation of this process). The stability of prototype p_j is then averaged over all test images in its category $c(j)$, and the overall score is the mean over all M prototypes.

Fig. 2. Visual example of the process of calculating stability (S_{sta}) for a single prototype on one image. Image extracted from Huang et al. (2023)[15].

This example highlights how minor perturbations can affect prototype activation maps and underscores the importance of robustness in interpretability evaluations.

3.3 Towards Enhanced Prototype Interpretability

Since the stability score introduced by Huang et al. (2023)[15] relies on manually identified object parts to assess whether a prototype activation remains anchored to the same region, this process still demands costly annotations and may lead to problems in the scalability and applicability of the metric. To overcome these limitations, we propose the **Structural Stability Score** (S_{ss}) which eliminates manual part labeling, and calculates the Stability with a prototype activation area comparison process. In addition, we propose the use of a closed set of transformations (defined in section 3.1), in order to calculate the stability against different transformations and to determine which is the visual characteristic against which each prototype is less stable.

To better understand our proposal, it is necessary to define the way in which two activations maps are compared and scored. The process is as follows:

1. **Activation Area Comparison:** The activation area comparison process consists of different phases: **(1)** First, let $V_1, \in [0, 1]^{H \times W}$ be the activation map of prototype p_j over the image x . **(2)** The activation map is then binarized by assigning a value of 1 to activations above γ , and 0 to activations below γ ; $B(\bar{V}_1) = \{\mathbf{1}(\bar{V}_1 \geq \gamma) \ \& \ \mathbf{0}(\bar{V}_1 < \gamma)\}$. **(3)** Now, let $V_2, \in [0, 1]^{H \times W}$ be the activation map of the prototype p_j over the perturbed image x_d . Repeat the previous process to calculate $B(\bar{V}_2)$. **(4)** Finally, we calculate the *Jaccard Index*, also known as Intersection over Union (IoU), on both maps (Eq. 3).

$$J(B(\bar{V}_1), B(\bar{V}_2)) = \frac{|B(\bar{V}_1) \cap B(\bar{V}_2)|}{|B(\bar{V}_1) \cup B(\bar{V}_2)|}. \quad (3)$$

2. **Maximum Activation Distance:** To avoid falling into the analysis of the activation area only, this metric also evaluates the displacement of the maximum peak of the activation after the transformation of the image: **(1)** First we calculate the Euclidean distance between each maximum activation peak, $d(\bar{V}_1, \bar{V}_2) = \|\arg \max \bar{V}_1 - \arg \max \bar{V}_2\|_2$. **(2)** Then, knowing that both activation maps have the same dimensions ($H \times W$), the maximum possible distance is calculated, $d_{\max} = \sqrt{(H-1)^2 + (W-1)^2}$. **(3)** Finally, the distance between the maximum peaks is normalized (scaled to lie between 0 and 1) and the similarity is calculated as shown in Eq. 4.

$$S_d(\bar{V}_1, \bar{V}_2) = 1 - \frac{d(\bar{V}_1, \bar{V}_2)}{d_{\max}}. \quad (4)$$

3. **Weighted Sum:** The numerical value of the comparison between two activation maps (such as \bar{V}_1 and \bar{V}_2) will be composed of the two parts previously calculated: the Jaccard's coefficient between the binarized maps, and the similarity of the Euclidean distance between the maximum activation peaks. Finally, the weighted sum of each coefficient is calculated to obtain a single value, as seen in Eq. 5.

$$f_s(\bar{V}_1, \bar{V}_2) = w \cdot J(B(\bar{V}_1), B(\bar{V}_2)) + (1 - w) \cdot S_d(\bar{V}_1, \bar{V}_2), \quad w \in [0, 1]. \quad (5)$$

Fig. 3 visually represents this stability calculation process. Knowing how two activation maps are compared, the next step is to integrate this process into the equation of the stability calculation. First, as one of the fundamental pillars of this metric is to be able to calculate the stability against different perturbations (and not only against Gaussian noise), we must define a set of transformations with which the images will be perturbed. In this case, we use the same set as the one proposed in the paper ‘‘This Looks Like That, Because... Explaining Prototypes for Interpretable Image Recognition’’ [19] and add the Gaussian noise transformation proposed in the original stability formula (See Eq. 2). Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 visually show how different transformations can affect the stability calculation. In addition, we do a comparison between a stable prototype and an unstable prototype.

From now on, the expression $\bar{V}^{p_j}(x)$ will refer to the activation map of prototype p_j on image x , and $\phi_i(x)$, will refer to an image x perturbed with the transformation

Fig. 3. Visual representation of the process of calculating the stability of a prototype. The process compares the activation map of the prototype on the original image and on the transformed image.

$\phi_i \in \Phi$. So the activation map of a prototype over a perturbed image will be expressed as $\bar{V}^{pj}(\phi_i(x))$. Eq. 7 shows how the Structural Stability Score of a Part-Prototype Network against a ϕ_i transformation is calculated.

$$\Phi = \{f_{\text{Contrast}}(x), f_{\text{Saturation}}(x), f_{\text{Hue}}(x), f_{\text{Shape}}(x), f_{\text{Texture}}(x), f_{\text{Noise}}(x)\}. \quad (6)$$

$$S_{ss}^{\phi_i} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{j=1}^M \frac{\sum_{x \in \mathcal{I}_{c(j)}} f_s \{ \bar{V}^{pj}(x), \bar{V}^{pj}(\phi_i(x)) \}}{\|\mathcal{I}_{c(j)}\|}, \quad \phi_i \in \Phi. \quad (7)$$

In summary, this research provides a comprehensive metric for prototype-based models by seamlessly integrating two complementary criteria: the overlap of activation regions (quantified via the Jaccard index) and the normalized Euclidean proximity of activation peaks. This dual assessment not only offers a more faithful spatial consistency measure under a diverse set of perturbations, but also indicates the specific transformation to which each prototype is most sensitive. Furthermore, by relying on a closed set of predefined transformations, our metric achieves both extensibility and scalability, enabling effortless adaptation to emerging perturbation types and large-scale vision tasks.

4 Experiments

In order to validate the efficacy and robustness of our proposed metric, we design a set of experiments that evaluate how prototype-based models behave under various visual perturbations.

Fig. 4. Calculation of the stability of a prototype against different transformations in the input image. A threshold, γ , of 0.6 is set for the binarization and a coefficient w of 0.65 for the weighted sum.

Fig. 5. Calculation of the stability of an unstable prototype against different transformations in the input image. A threshold, γ , of 0.6 is set for the binarization and a coefficient w of 0.65 for the weighted sum.

4.1 Experimental Setting

Datasets. All experiments are conducted on the CUB-200-2011 dataset [23], a fine-grained bird classification benchmark consisting of 11,788 images across 200 species, each annotated with bounding boxes, segmentations, and part-level attributes. Follow-

ing prior work on prototype-based interpretability [19,15,6], we train and evaluate our models under the same train/test split and preprocessing protocols.

Model Configurations. We instantiate two variants of our prototype-based model differing only in backbone architecture using both *Resnet34* backbone and *VGG19* backbone. Both variants are trained end-to-end, optimizing the classification loss alongside prototype clustering and separation terms, in accordance with the implementation details of [6,19].

Parameters. Regarding the dimensions of the prototype activation maps, we set H , W to be 7 and 7. For the first stability calculation, we set γ and w to be 0.5 both (in tables 2, 3 and 4, we test with different configurations of these parameters). Our models are trained for 15 epochs with the Adam optimizer (including 5 epochs for warm-up). We set the learning rates of the backbone, the add-on module, and the prototypes to be $1e^{-4}$, $3e^{-3}$, and $3e^{-3}$, respectively. The number of prototypes per category and the dimension of prototypes is set to 10 and 128 for our method.

4.2 Stability Evaluation

We assess model robustness by measuring Structural Stability Score under the six different transformations defined in the Eq. 6: noise, contrast, saturation, hue, shape and texture. For the Gaussian Noise transformation we set σ to 0.2, the rest of the transformations maintain the parameters of the paper “This Looks Like That, Because... Explaining Prototypes for Interpretable Image Recognition” [19]. Table 1 reports these scores for VGG19 and Resnet34 with $\gamma = 0.5$, $w = 0.5$. The results in the table demonstrate how the stability of a model varies based on the transformation applied, allowing a better understanding of how prototypes respond to visual perturbations at the time of inference.

Table 1. Average Stability results for Resnet34 and VGG19, for each different transformation, using $\gamma = 0.5$ and $w = 0.5$

Stability	Noise	Contrast	Saturation	Hue	Shape	Texture	Avg Stability
VGG19	0,7529	0,8157	0,8065	0,7269	0,8307	0,6924	0,7709
Resnet34	0,8087	0,8391	0,8459	0,7406	0,8386	0,7537	0,8044

4.3 Hyperparameter Sensitivity for Stability

We next examine how the weighting parameter w and the binarization threshold γ influence prototype stability. Due to the hard discrimination made by the first metric (labeling as unstable any prototype that fails to activate just on one part of the inferred object), it is necessary to study our sensitivity to slight changes in the hyperparameters. Tables 2, 3 and 4, report Avg Stability under $(w, \gamma) \in \{0.5, 0.65, 0.8\} \times \{0.5, 0.7\}$.

In both backbones, higher w (higher importance to Jaccard’s coefficient in the weighted sum) tends to score stability lower, particularly for texture. On the other hand, a larger w (more restrictive binarization) tends to score the stability of the models

Table 2. Stability results for Resnet34 and VGG19 using $w = 0.5$ and $\gamma = 0.5, 0.7$, for each different transformation.

Stability	$w = 0,50$			
	$\gamma = 0,5$		$\gamma = 0,7$	
Transformation	VGG19	Resnet34	VGG19	Resnet34
Noise	0,7529	0,8087	0,7081	0,7595
Contrast	0,8157	0,8391	0,7776	0,7946
Saturation	0,8065	0,8459	0,7682	0,8022
Hue	0,7269	0,7406	0,6831	0,6833
Shape	0,8307	0,8386	0,7946	0,7938
Texture	0,6924	0,7537	0,6410	0,6956
Avg Stability	0,7709	0,8044	0,7288	0,7548

Table 3. Stability results for Resnet34 and VGG19 using $w = 0.65$ and $\gamma = 0.5, 0.7$, for each different transformation.

Stability	$w = 0,65$			
	$\gamma = 0,5$		$\gamma = 0,7$	
Transformation	VGG19	Resnet34	VGG19	Resnet34
Noise	0,7183	0,7802	0,6601	0,7162
Contrast	0,7886	0,8147	0,7391	0,7570
Saturation	0,7781	0,8224	0,7284	0,7656
Hue	0,6869	0,7002	0,6299	0,6257
Shape	0,8058	0,8145	0,7587	0,7563
Texture	0,6473	0,7166	0,5804	0,6412
Avg Stability	0,7375	0,7748	0,6828	0,7103

Table 4. Stability results for Resnet34 and VGG19 using $w = 0.80$ and $\gamma = 0.5, 0.7$, for each different transformation.

Stability	$w = 0,80$			
	$\gamma = 0,5$		$\gamma = 0,7$	
Transformation	VGG19	Resnet34	VGG19	Resnet34
Noise	0,6837	0,7904	0,6122	0,6729
Contrast	0,7617	0,7990	0,7006	0,7193
Saturation	0,7497	0,6598	0,6885	0,7291
Hue	0,6469	0,7905	0,5767	0,5681
Shape	0,7809	0,6795	0,7230	0,7187
Texture	0,6022	0,7517	0,5199	0,5867
Avg Stability	0,7042	0,7452	0,6368	0,6658

higher. For our metric, Resnet34 consistently outperforms VGG19 in terms of stability, although this does not always mean better model performance.

5 Conclusions

This work introduces the **Structural Stability Score** (S_{ss}), an automated metric designed to assess the stability of prototype activations in ProtoPNet without requiring manual part annotations. Rather than comparing how a prototype activates on the same

part of an object before and after perturbing an image, S_{ss} quantifies the stability by measuring the similarity of two activation maps under a diverse set of visual transformations, including changes in noise, contrast, saturation, hue, shape, and texture.

This metric helps us better understand how interpretable a prototype truly is: stable prototypes suggest that the model has learned reliable and robust associations, while unstable ones reveal fragility in the explanatory process. The S_{ss} metric allows us to probe the explanatory behavior of the model in a systematic and scalable way, making it possible to examine interpretability across large datasets without subjective judgments or annotation costs.

In future work, we aim to expand this methodology in three directions: **(1)** Develop optimization strategies to accelerate the computation of S_{ss} , enabling large-scale analysis; **(2)** Extend this approach to the concept of *consistency* across prototypes, with the goal of achieving a fully automated, quantitative, and objective framework for interpretability assessment; and **(3)** Integrate stability and consistency metrics directly into the training loss, encouraging models to learn not only accurate but also interpretable and robust representations. Through these efforts, we hope to bridge the gap between transparency and performance in prototype-based models.

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